

**RETHINKING HEALTH
SYSTEM DESIGN**

**TOWARDS A
HIGH VALUE
HEALTH SYSTEM MODEL**

PREPARED BY
HEALTH SYSTEMS INNOVATION LAB
AT HARVARD UNIVERSITY

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About the position paper

This position paper, *Towards A High Value Health Systems Model*, was developed under the guidance of Professor Rifat Atun, Professor of Global Health Systems at Harvard University and Director of the Health Systems Innovation Lab, and implemented by a team consisting of Dr Che L. Reddy, Associate Director *Health Systems Innovation Lab, Harvard University*, Johnattan Garcia Ruiz, Senior Associate, *Health Systems Innovation Lab, Harvard University*, and with the support of Dr Bryan Tan, Visiting Scientist at *Health Systems Innovation Lab, Harvard University*. The ideas, insights and frameworks in this position paper are drawn from earlier research, publications, and collaborative initiatives led by Professor Rifat Atun at the Health System Innovation Lab at Harvard University.

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Terminologies and concepts

Conceptual clarity is crucial for promoting a common understanding of transitioning to high value health systems, the central argument of this paper. The following four terms are used frequently throughout this position paper:

Health system: We locate health systems within a complex systems framework designed to improve the level and distribution of health, financial protection, and user satisfaction for populations.¹ Health systems are characterised by interacting functions and dynamic complexity and are shaped by multiple actors (institutions, individuals) and contextual factors in each country or setting.^{2,3,4}

Health services: health services are the overarching output of health systems, encompassing services delivered at the individual level (medical care) or the population level (public health).^{1,2} Medical care entails any interaction and intervention between patients and healthcare providers along a continuum of care from screening to palliation. Public health services include those that are promoting (advancing wellness, happiness, and contentment), protective (minimising the effect of health threats), and preventing (limiting disease emergence, progression, and complications) in nature.¹

High value health system (HVHS): transitioning to a high value health system requires the development and implementation of 10 components (discussed in detail in subsequent sections of this paper) with the purpose of achieving “value for money” and “value for many.”^{5,6} A high value health system produces system outputs (individual and population level health services) designed to meet health system objectives of effectiveness and efficiency (value for money), as well as equity and responsiveness (value for many).

Innovation: any policy, program, intervention, technology, or institutional arrangement perceived as novel by the system and adopters.⁷⁻⁹

Why transition to a high-value health system?

Introduction

This position paper discusses a major, and arguably one of the most critical developments in comparative health systems: the transition towards a high value health system model.^{1,6} High value health systems have one goal: to produce impact, at scale, for entire populations, over the long term by creating “value for money and value for many.”^{1,5,6} The paper draws on major theoretical research, empirical data, unpublished perspectives, and country experiences to provide a critical review of the literature in comparative health systems to develop the empirical basis and rationale for high value health systems.

The paper is organised in three sections. Section one focuses on the current state of and major shifts that influence contemporary health systems and discusses the current signs of systems fatigue. In section two, we build on this analysis and outline each of the ten components that need to be in place to establish a high-value health system and discuss illustrative examples from G20+ countries that have used one or more of these components to transition to high value health systems. In the third section, we provide a strategy to help countries to transition to a high-value health system model.

Diagnosing ailing health systems

The role of health systems for the health, economic and societal well-being of populations could never be more important. The major shifts acting on health systems today are unprecedented in scale and intensity, with few signs of abating. These include, among others, rising citizen expectations and demands of healthcare,^{10,11} the direct and indirect effects of climate change on health,^{12,13} demographic transitions and epidemiological shifts,^{14,15} including the sequelae of the

COVID-19 pandemic,^{16,17} economic constraints,¹⁸ flawed democracies and heightened political participation,^{19,20} and technological disruption.^{21,22}

Contemporary health systems are not adapting to manage these major shifts effectively, are strained beyond their capability, and exhibiting signs of system failure. How do we know that health systems are failing and what is the root cause of this failure? There are two cardinal signs, namely the inability to respond and be resilient to contextual shifts that occur due to external shocks and internal stressors to maintain system performance.

The first sign of failure relates to the inability to mount an effective *response* to contextual shifts to maintain system performance to continue to produce desired results and outcomes. Health systems exist to produce desirable outcomes in terms of health, user satisfaction, and financial risk protection.²³ While there have been notable achievements in global health convergence and more investment in health,^{24–26} there are concerning signs that crucial outcomes are either plateauing or, worse, reversing. In the United States of America, a high-income country (HIC) that spends more on health as a proportion of Gross Domestic Product compared to any other nation,²⁷ the average life expectancy has been falling since 2014, and the Maternal Mortality Rate has more than doubled since 1995—with major disparities in terms of income and race.^{28–31} In the United Kingdom (UK), another HIC, junior doctors in the National Health Service, express their dissatisfaction with the health system by striking.³² While this is not unique to the UK,³³ there is a global workforce crisis in health systems, exacerbated by COVID-19, characterised by low morale and high levels of physician burnout.³⁴ In low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs), it is estimated that five billion people cannot access life or limb-saving surgical healthcare and 33 million people fall further into poverty when accessing such care.³⁵ Yet, across the board, countries are paying more for health as a proportion of their economic output than ever before.³⁶

A lack of *resilience* and stability is the second sign of systems failure. Health systems must adapt dynamically to stabilise core functions and delivery of health services over time. During the COVID-19 pandemic, an estimated 50 million surgical operations were cancelled, nearly a sixth of all operations that take place annually worldwide,³⁷⁻³⁹ but the total surgical backlog is much larger⁴⁰ and will take years to manage.⁴¹ Long-term stresses such as those that have occurred in Brazil following changes in political administration and economic austerity have led to adverse effects in health system investments and compromised the major achievements of the Unified Health System in advancing Universal Health Coverage.⁴²

When health systems cannot use and rapidly scale innovations that are proven effective, they underperform and cannot meet user demands efficiently, responsively, and equitably at the system level.⁶ Among G20+ countries that subscribe to the four-drug regimen for secondary prevention of adverse cardiac events, few health systems could provide these agents to eligible patients. Only a few countries with available data provided all four therapeutic agents to more than 50% of the patients that required secondary prevention.⁴³ In sub-Saharan Africa, out of every ten people with hypertension, health systems diagnose four and put two on treatment; only one person has their blood pressure controlled.⁴⁴ The inability of health systems to deliver evidence-based interventions at scale to respond to long-term stressors such as chronic diseases leads to needless deaths from preventable conditions or medical complications.

The aetiology of health system failure

Many reasons contribute to health systems failure, including, among others, workforce challenges,^{45,46} persistent funding deficits,^{36,47} problems relating to the nature of healthcare

services and challenges to delivery,^{48–50} access to healthcare and disparities,^{51,52} the “politics of health”,^{53–55} medical errors and medico-legal claims,^{56,57} rising cost of healthcare,^{58,59} inability to address unmet healthcare needs.⁶⁰ In our organising framework, we adopt a systems approach but recognise and draw on other scholarly perspectives^{61–67} (Appendix A, Panel 1) that advance our collective understanding of health systems. In our view, an interpretive framework anchored in a system’s mode of analysis^{1,2,5,6} (Diagram 1) is paramount for diagnosing problems and their root causes and developing innovations for addressing them in a context-sensitive manner.

Diagram 1: Health Systems Framework

Source: Atun R, Moore G. *Building a High-Value Health System*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2021 DOI:10.1093/oso/9780197528549.001.0001.⁶

The imperative to rethink health system design

Health system reform efforts focus excessively on ‘inputs’. Yet, it is not input that determines how well a health system performs but how well a country designs its health system to provide “value for money” and “value for many”. How much money goes into health systems is just one factor

that influences health system behaviour and performance. Across all nations, the most critical ingredient for creating high value health systems to achieve large-scale population benefit is system design underpinned by strategic change. There is a major opportunity for innovation in the design of health systems and for cross-country learning. We propose a framework to develop a high value health system.

What is a high-value health system?

Redesigning Health Systems for Value

Transition to a high-value health system requires ten interdependent and mutually reinforcing design components, as outlined in *Transition to Health Systems: A Primer*.⁶ These include: (I) digital data systems, (II) analytics, (III) cost measurement systems, (IV) outcomes measurement systems, (V) benchmarking, (VI) integrated care pathways with bundled services, (VII) value-based payment models, (VIII) value-based procurement, (IX) integrated provider networks, and (X) strategic change and innovation ecosystem. Countries that invest in these ten components are more likely to unlock far greater efficiency, responsiveness, equity, and effectiveness in their health systems over the long term than countries that do not. We discuss each of these components in turn.

The 10 Components of a High Value Health System

Component 1: Digital data systems

HVHS Component	Value-creating elements
Digital data systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Digital data platforms: to enable collection, reporting, and pooling of digital data via electronic medical records for health, wellness and across the care continuum• Standardization: shared definitions, formats and language• Integrated data sets: ability to pool and link different data forms (text, waveform, image, among others) from multiple sources• Modular architecture: architecture that provides for agility and flexible design and scale-up• Interoperability: enabling seamless exchange of data between multiple data sources and data systems• Data governance and stewardship: to ensure data security and privacy

Health systems generate a copious amount of data, yet few harness these data optimally to enhance system performance and generate value. Many countries still collect a large amount of data on

paper, with fragmented approaches to data management. A High-Value Health System uses digital data as a critical resource to optimise health system functions and deliver high value health services at population and individual levels.

Multiple countries from the G20 have adopted Electronic Health Records (EHRs), Electronic Medical Records (EMRs) and Personal Health Records (PHRs) in their health systems, but diffusion is far from uniform. Indeed, many of the advantages digital data systems promise have yet to be realised for generating value.⁶⁸ Much progress has been made globally to advance standardisation in medical terminologies that enable information to be shared digitally between actors in health systems.^{69,70} Nevertheless, there are still substantial challenges with the interoperability of data systems, data stewardship, and the use of data to inform value capture at health systems level.⁷¹ While the implementation of data systems can be costly in monetary terms and for healthcare workers, as examples in the USA demonstrate,^{72,73} the field is ripe for innovation. Technologies exist for the implementation of cost-efficient solutions that harness the cloud to combine and integrate multiple data formats, and platforms that understand human language⁷⁴ to help inform decisions to streamline the patient encounter.

The Republic of Armenia introduced a digital data system at the national level, ArMed. This platform collects clinical, administrative, and financial information that benefits patients, providers, payers, and the government. ArMed is managed by the National Electronic Healthcare Operator (CJSC), a private joint venture responsible for technical management and improvement of the system, subscriber and user service, software maintenance, and user training.⁷⁵ ArMed provides the Ministry of Health with a centralized information repository that has enabled it to inform decision-making around resource optimization, care delivery, and planning at the national level.⁷⁶

Estonia, for instance, is considered one of the leading countries in adopting, developing, and evolving a digital health system. Since 1994, the Estonian government committed to respond social challenges through an information technology approach, and from 2001, the ‘X-road,’ became the national integration platform that today serves as the backbone of e-Estonia.⁷⁷ In 2008, this Nordic country launched its e-Health initiative, a nationwide system that would integrate data from Estonia’s healthcare providers using Electronic Health Records.⁷⁸ From then, more health services are being taking advantage of the benefits of digital health data systems, including a hospital information system, digital prescriptions, e-consultations and even e-ambulances.⁷⁹ The Estonian digital health system provided a strong response to the COVID-19 pandemic, not only by offering telemedicine solutions (already implemented long before the global health emergency), but also to support the payment mechanism behind these services through the Estonian Health Insurance Fund.⁸⁰ The developing of an e-Health ecosystem has granted Estonia wide international recognition, claiming the top position of the HIMSS Annual European Digital Health Survey in 2021 and 2019, and the #SmartHealthSystems: Digital Health Index in 2018.⁸¹

Component 2: Analytics

HVHS Component	Value-creating elements
Analytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced data science capabilities: to combine, harness and analyze digital data, among others, on user citizen characteristics, interventions, cost, process, utilization, and outcomes using machine learning, artificial intelligence, and advanced simulation modelling to improve policy and practice • Reporting: sharing of relevant analyses to inform health system decisions aimed at improving performance

Analytics is critical for value creation and to ascertain if value is being achieved. Collecting health data is only likely to help in value creation if these data are appropriately analysed to guide

decision-making for providers, payers, citizens, patients, and regulators at all levels of a health system. Areas where analytics could play a role include, among others, in measuring costs, access, outcomes, in informing service design, the development of a suitable portfolio of interventions for target population groups, in improving resource allocation, investment decisions, process efficiency and user engagement, and to enable research and innovation.⁷¹

Analytics encompasses a range of statistics and advanced data science techniques, including machine learning, to reveal patterns, trends, associations, and future predictions from large volumes of data that would be difficult using human intelligence. A major challenge to the widespread use of analytics in health systems has been the lack of curated data sets to enable the application of novel data science methods such as machine learning. To generate value from analytical capabilities, health system stakeholders must establish appropriate data governance and stewardship frameworks and consider how the outputs of analyses will be used to improve, among others, processes, outputs and outcomes to achieve greater value for money and value for many.⁷¹

The Republic of Korea created a set of indicators used to develop disease registries that extract relevant data to inform policymaking at the system level. A Health Insurance Review and Assessment Agency implemented a Benefits Information Analysis System, a solution that gathers information from different agencies to analyse trends in the frequency and cost of medical interventions and select outcomes to prevent unnecessary healthcare services and errors.⁸² Through this initiative, the Korean Government can monitor the use of services and resources, provide valuable statistics to promote trust and inform public health campaigns and policies.⁸²

Component 3: Cost measurement systems

HVHS Component	Value-creating elements
Cost measurement systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Harmonized definition and measurement: established framework and process that are used by providers, payers, researchers and policy makers to measure cost of care and illness and activities in health systems• Automation: seamless extraction of measured cost data from digital data systems to enable value-based payment• Labelling: data tagging in terms of time and location to ascertain the time and resources allocated to different activities• Comparative benchmarking: holistic view of healthcare costs among and between providers, payers and patients with capacity to perform comparative analyses.

Although all actors in the health system bear a cost when seeking, providing, using, or paying for health, dominant actors try and shift cost to others in a zero-sum game.⁶² Such actions detract from value capture and hinder transition to high value health systems. Hence, there is a need to create a culture of interdependence, collaboration and collective action to generate value for all at individual and population level. All actors have an essential role and responsibility to achieve this objective by managing costs effectively and efficiently. A harmonised methodology for measuring and reporting costs is a critical ingredient for efforts aimed at measuring and optimising cost, enhancing investment decisions and inform efficient payment mechanisms in health systems.

Currently, there is a wide variation on the methods and approaches used to measure cost in health systems and how to incorporate such measurements in informing practice and policy of payers and healthcare providers at both institutional and system levels. High-Value Health Systems harmonise, invest, promote clarity, and streamline processes to measure, report and track costs easily. Such cost measurement systems require providers to register relevant data on cost across the entire care pathway.

In Australia, the Independent Health and Aged Care Pricing Authority (IHACPA) manages the National Hospital Cost Data Collection Reports, which collects hospital cost and activity information by the Australian Refined Diagnosis Related Groups.⁸³ This information is used to calculate National Weighted Activity Units (NWAU) for health services lines.⁸⁴ For example, in the 2022-2023 determinations, a Tonsillectomy has a weight of 0.7400 NWAU, which equates to \$4,290, while a coronary artery bypass graft has a weight of 5.3925 NWAU, which equates to \$31,260. These determinations are established annually through a consultatory process and used to inform payments from National Health Funding Body⁸⁵ to public hospitals based on their reported activity in a year.⁸⁶ While there is a mandate to report expenses for public hospitals, private providers can participate voluntarily. The cost reports allow the Australian federal and local governments to calculate public spending on five types of services: admitted acute, emergency, non-admitted, sub-acute and non-acute, and ‘other’.⁸³ Each year, the collected data are analysed to develop publicly accessible reports and to provide recommendations to deliver more cost-efficient care.

Component 4: Outcome measurement systems

HVHS Component	Value-creating elements
Outcome measurement systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonised indicators • Harmonised measurement: established framework and process to jointly assess meaningful care and wellness outcomes for patients, providers and payers • PROMS: Implemented measuring tools to assess patients’ health status and well-being associated with the health services received • PREMS: Utilization of tracking mechanisms to assess patients’ experience and the quality of service provided • Comparative benchmarking: holistic view of outcomes among and between providers and payers with capacity to perform comparative detailed analysis.

As with cost measurement systems, there is a need to establish harmonised outcome measurement systems to develop High-Value Health Systems. Without a harmonised set of indicators and measurement systems, payers, providers, regulators, and the public are unable to assess the outcomes achieved and the extent to which health services are delivered with value.

There are many opportunities to create outcome measurement systems that reflect the inherent priorities in country health systems, but the level of adoption of such systems varies substantially. Several G20+ countries have implemented Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROMS) in their health system. In some cases, providers have led initiatives to measure outcomes later scaled to the national level (i.e., the Netherlands). In other cases, there has been a top-down mandate establishing PROMS at a national, federal, or regional level (i.e., the UK, Australia, and Switzerland). Others have implemented Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREMs), measurement tools to assess the quality of healthcare services during the patients' journeys. The Canadian Institute for Health Information, for instance, use PREMs to support patient-centered care in hospitals by providing key information to acute care providers regarding their users' perceptions on the care received.⁸⁷ In the US, Europe and Australia, the International Consortium for Health Outcome Measurement has supported health systems, payers, and providers in their efforts to develop harmonised outcome measures, ranging from an institution level as it is the case in the Santeon Hospitals in the Netherlands, to a network care level like the Blue Cross Blue Shield of Michigan, or a health system level like the National Health Service in England.⁸⁸

The OECD has established the Patient-Reported Indicator Surveys initiative—the PaRIS initiative, a multi-country collaboration on the development and harmonisation of indicators and measures of patient-related outcomes to improve performance of primary care through a patient-centred care approach. The initiative goes one step further than other strategies by including policymakers as

its users, encouraging health systems to use outcome measurements as critical indicators to inform quality improvement actions and priority-setting decisions.⁸⁹

The Quality and Outcomes Framework (QOF) of the National Health Systems (NHS) in the United Kingdom (UK), established in April 2004, aims to improve outcomes among General Practitioners (GPs) in the country and promote retention in the system.⁹⁰ The QOF provides a set of indicators that GPs must measure and report to achieve a certain number of points (which relate to desirable outcomes) each year.⁹¹ The QOF is updated annually to include revisions to the number of indicators, maximum number of points achievable, and the amount of funding per point achieved to remunerate GPs. The results of the QOF are published in the form of a report and publicly accessible online via an interactive dashboard.⁹² Although the QoF was initiated as a voluntary program, 99% of eligible GP practices participate in the QOF.

Component 5: Benchmarking

HVHS Component	Major value-creating elements
Performance benchmarking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comparative analysis and transparency: collection and analysis of data that enables comparison over time in a unit (longitudinal benchmarking) or across various units of salience (comparative benchmarking) in terms of level (primary healthcare vs public healthcare), department (surgery vs medical), and jurisdictions (national vs subnational)

The fifth component of the high value health system is benchmarking. Broadly, it refers to analysis of performance of health system outputs, in relation to effectiveness, efficiency, equity and responsiveness of the services delivered, and outcomes, in relation to health, financial protection and user satisfaction. Transparent benchmarking of performance reveals which departments, institutions, or regions perform better than others in relation to outputs and outcomes, offering the

possibility to formulate questions to understand why the observed variation exists, informs further analysis to identify the factors which account for the variation observed and help to formulate policies to reduce variation and improve performance. Benchmarking is only possible when elements of the components related to data systems, analytics and measurement frameworks are in place to enable the meaningful like-for-like comparisons.

Get It Right First Time (GIRFT) is an initiative developed in the UK that enables performance benchmarking across multiple healthcare provider institutions.⁹³ Initially developed to reduce variation and to enhance efficiency in the delivery of orthopedic healthcare services following the 2007-08 financial crisis-induced budgetary reforms in the National Health Service (NHS), the initiative has expanded to include 41 specialties, or medical conditions, where it reports performance data across participating NHS healthcare Trusts. GIRFT enables an understanding in terms of how facilities differ in terms of the population mix served, delivery of health services, the results achieved, cost of services and procedures, and the expenditures incurred, among others. All information is made publicly available, which is used to develop an annual report that summarises the findings.⁹⁴ Such comparative benchmarking information can reveal important insights into the performance of the NHS—particularly when combined with the QOF framework—to inform the design, implementation, and scale-up of innovations to improve performance across NHS Trusts and at the system level.

Component 6: Integrated care pathways with bundled services

HVHS Component	Major value-creating elements
Integrated care pathways with bundled services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pathways: evidenced-based standardisation of processes for healthcare services and actions aimed at promoting health • Analysis of variation: real-time analysis of variation of the care delivered compared to the pathway in use

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bundling: intervention bundling across the care continuum to promote improved efficiency, effectiveness, responsiveness, and equity of the care delivered and to improve outcomes • Stratification: categorisation of individuals and patients into subgroups – for example categorized by level of risk, patient characteristics or disease complexity – to enable dedicated care pathways with targeted interventions for each subgroup
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Health systems are complex, with various healthcare services and activities distributed across one’s home and the community, as well as primary, secondary and tertiary levels. This tiered and compartmentalised service model often produces fragmented care⁹⁵ that lacks coordination, leading to inefficient care delivery and adversely impacting generation of value. Enhanced navigation through health systems could be achieved through integrated delivery systems that bundle related services and activities within and across different tiers of care. Integrated delivery systems are organised, coordinated, and collaborative networks that link various healthcare providers to provide a coordinated and seamless continuum of services to a particular patient population or community centred on the care journey. ICPs provide a way to improve health outcomes and reduce costs through greater coordination and delivery of person-centred care across the care continuum.⁹⁷

The extent of coordination occurs along two axes along the health systems delivery continuum (Figure 1). First, the extent of intervention bundling intervention, ranging from a technology (for example, making available a new diagnostic test, a vaccine, a medicine), to single episode of care (such as the administration of a vaccine to the insertion of a cardiac defibrillator, or the provision of a hip operation), to management of a single disease (such as diabetes, high blood pressure, HIV, or tuberculosis), or multiple diseases (for example cardiovascular disease (management of risk factors such as obesity, low-exercise levels, diabetes, high blood pressure, high cholesterol levels,

ischaemic heart disease), to the population level. Second, the extent of scale-up ranging from a single department to the entire health system. More details of the bundling approach across the two dimensions are further elaborated in the Health System Innovation Lab publication “Transition to High Value Health Systems: A Primer” .⁶

Figure 1: Health systems delivery continuum

Source: Atun R. Transition to High Value Health Systems: A Primer. Health Systems Innovation Lab. Harvard University, 2022, Boston, MA, USA.

In 2016, the Ministry of Health in Singapore introduced the “Three Beyonds” strategy with one of the key strategic thrusts of moving “Beyond Quality to Value”.⁹⁸ As part of the initiative, bundle payments for various conditions were introduced. These payment reforms inspired providers to change how care was delivered. Specifically for managing hip fractures, the strategy transitioned from a single hospital clinical pathway to an integrated care model between acute and community

hospitals through the entire care continuum encompassing initial admission, inpatient surgical care, and rehabilitation. The new model led to major improvements⁹⁹ in the efficiency of the care delivered and helped to reduce cost of care provided. In 2022, the Ministry of Health of Singapore announced another major initiative, “HealthierSG”,¹⁰⁰ that catalysed further changes in the ICP and service bundling spectrum. A transition to a capitation model for each of the three healthcare clusters (networks of healthcare providers) with a particular emphasis on primary care, building an integrated health and social ecosystem, and preventative care, with the objective of shifting bundling further upstream with improved care integration toward primary and secondary prevention of hip fractures in the community through targeted interventions.

Component 7: Value-based payment models

HVHS Component	Major value-creating elements
Value based payment models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value based remuneration: provider payments based on improvements in achieving outcomes and reducing cost of care delivered and the value achieved across the care cycle • Risk/reward alignment: mapping of risk / reward balance to inform level of incentives and payments for the outcomes achieved

A value-based health system aims to ensure that funding for healthcare services, and technologies shifts from a transaction that follow inputs or activity to a model where payment and rewards follow the achievement of value – in terms of improved efficiency, effectiveness, responsiveness and equity, in order to realise for users, providers and payers value for money and value for many. High-Value Health Systems reward outcomes, align risk and reward (by providing greater reward where risk of failure to achieve an outcome is higher or where the interventions target ‘higher-risk’ patients in terms of unmet need and the complexity of condition), and design novel incentive structures to enable all stakeholders to contribute towards value creation at the system level.

There are several payment methods such as Diagnosis Related Groups (DRG), Case-Based Payments (CBP), Bundled Payments, or Case Mix Funding (CMF) combined with outcomes that could be leveraged to develop value-based payment models. Bundled payments, an arrangement whereby providers are remunerated for providing a bundle of healthcare services and a target for achieving an outcome level for a medical condition (Heart Failure), or a medical event (Acute Myocardial Infarction) have been implemented in several countries, including Australia, Canada, France, Netherlands, Norway, United Kingdom, and the United States, with positive results in outcomes when combined with a target for quality of care in the payment models.¹⁰¹

In 2015, the United States enacted the Medicare Access and CHIP Reauthorization Act (MACRA). Among its provisions, were substantial changes in the way in which Medicare doctors were to be reimbursed. To implement these payment changes, the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid (CMS) established the Quality Payment Program (QPP) to reward value and to curb cost in one of two ways: a Merit-based Incentive Payment System (MIPS) or an Advanced Alternative Payment Model (APM).¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁴ MIPS required clinicians to report information in four value-enhancing areas: quality, improvement activities, promoting interoperability and cost. Depending on the clinicians’ score (0-100) in relation to the performance threshold, CMS could apply a positive, neutral or negative adjustment to the clinicians’ Medicare reimbursement.⁹²

Component 8: Value-based procurement

HVHS Component	Major value-creating elements
Value based procurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value orientation: shift from purchasing inputs or “things” to payment for an overall outcome • Risk / reward alignment: sharing of risk and reward between vendors and providers • Pooling: bulk purchasing

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply chain: integration of procurement within supply chain management systems, including inventory optimization, underpinned by data systems
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Procurement refers to the purchasing of goods (infrastructure, equipment, medications, and supplies) or services required to deliver health care. In conventional forms of procurement a healthcare provider purchases goods from a vendor, which is typically a private entity. Common forms of procurement include purchasing medications from pharmaceutical companies. Procurement processes are often hampered with many challenges leading to inefficiency and suboptimal value for patients, providers and payers, including, among others: (I) lack of transparency in the process, cost, and quality of goods, (II) variable quality of goods, (III) variable cost of goods, (IV) lack of inputs from healthcare practitioners that use procured goods; (V) undue emphasis on cost and volume; (VI) decoupling of the goods procured from the clinical service delivered, and (VIII) no guarantee that the procured goods will be used appropriately to lead to improvements in outcomes.

Value-based procurement differs from conventional procurement processes in that it takes a longer and more holistic view to engage vendors. Vendors are approached for providing not just a device, health technology or a medicinal product but solutions in which a payment decision considers the role of a product in delivering an outcome, for example in relation to improved efficiency, effectiveness, responsiveness or equity.^{105,106} Emphasis is placed on adopting a longer-term view to procurement over time rather than a short-term transaction focused on paying for a product at the lowest possible cost – decisions that are often made by procurement specialists that are not involved in clinical care. Value based procurement emphasises:

- Solutions: considering how a product or technology could deliver better value healthcare to benefit all concerned;
- Collaboration: involvement of users of the procured solution (clinicians and patients);
- Risk-reward: balancing risk and reward between vendors and health providers.

A value-based procurement initiative was introduced and implemented at Southlake Regional Health Center in Ontario, Canada.¹⁰⁷ The Cardiac Care Program, which provides both surgical and medical cardiac healthcare services, reconfigured its conventional procurement process, which was managed by a dedicated procurement department in the hospital. The main components of the new procurement process entailed: 1) establishing a multidisciplinary team that would be responsible for developing the new procurement arrangement; 2) involving physicians in vendor dialogue and negotiation; 3) developing metrics to measure procurement performance in terms of four value dimensions: cost, innovation, operational and patient; 4) linking procurement with the delivery of healthcare services; 5) implementing a dynamic change management program to develop the necessary mindset and relationships for vendors and providers to share risk and reward in the delivery of healthcare services through the procurement process.

As a result, the program partnered with Medtronic Integrate Health Solutions to facilitate patients access to better quality of care through the procurement of new devices based not only on price but also on outcome measures.¹⁰⁷ This value-based relationship has fostered new opportunities for value creation, as Southlake and Medtronic have engaged in new partnerships to improve efficiency and waiting times. For instance, in 2019, Medtronic supported the Southlake's Cardiac Short Stay Unit to reduce to zero procedure cancellations and improve service delays.

Component 9: Integrated provider networks

HVHS Component	Major value-creating elements
Integrated provider networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Operational integration: collaboration for bundling of healthcare service provision using shared integrated care pathway across several providers and levels• Structural integration: of providers via affiliation or mergers to develop integrated care networks that enable provision of seamless care across a pathway

Health systems are currently supply-side driven and are not functionally organised around patients or the care process. As a result, users face fragmented care journeys that adversely affect the effectiveness, efficiency, responsiveness, and equity of care provided. Providers need to organise the care process to deliver person-centered health services in a more interdisciplinary, collaborative, and integrated fashion that enables leveraging necessary capabilities, and resources to address a health problem. This can be achieved through ‘operational integration’, where different providers share a common integrated care pathway, or by developing integrated provider networks that allow bundling of services within and between levels of health care or across multiple sectors (for example, health and social sectors).

An exciting example of an effective application of this component is Germany’s ‘Gesundes Kinzigtal’ program. In 2005, a joint venture of a health sciences-based management company and an interdisciplinary physician and psychotherapist network created a population-based integrated care program for the citizens of the State of Baden-Württemberg.¹⁰⁸ The network comprised health professionals, hospitals, clinics, nursing homes, pharmacies, and physiotherapies. The program partnered with fitness centres and sports clubs, enabling users to access multiple levels of care without facing fragmented services. At the same time, the providers created new interactions that improved communication, information, and the quality of respect for the citizens.

Component 10: Strategic change and innovation ecosystem

HVHS Component	Major value-creating elements
<i>Strategic change and innovation ecosystem</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Strategic public-private partnerships Leadership: top level commitment to high value health system transformation within government, with strong collaborative working arrangement with sub-national levels and private sector that promotes trust• Innovation ecosystem: institutionalization of push and pull strategies and policy changes that promote ‘emergent’ and ‘driven’ innovation to encourage innovation design, development, implementation and scale-up to transform a health system for value creation,

Many innovations in health care that promote a value-based approach stem from in-house intrapreneurs among provider or payer groups. Some find opportunities to scale up their activities (from departments inside an institution to a whole network of care or even up to a health system level) or to expand their innovations to include new interventions (from a single therapy solution to a population-level strategy). However, the transition to a High-Value Health System requires strategic change and the creation of an innovation ecosystem that supports emergent and driven innovations through appropriate policies and by the implementation of ‘push’ strategies (financial support for research, development, commercialisation and implementation testing) and ‘pull’ strategies (signalling that funding will be available for adoption and diffusion of innovations).⁶ (See Atun R. Transition to High Value Health Systems: A Primer. Health Systems Innovation Lab. Harvard University, 2022, Boston, MA, USA)

The design and transition to a High-Value Health System is a complex system innovation, instead of a collection of individual endeavours, which requires active effort for strategic change and the alignment of multiple stakeholders for its adoption and diffusion.¹⁰⁹ In 2017, for example, the Ministry of Health of Catalunya, in Spain, launched its ‘Catalan Information System Master Plan,’ a digital health strategy to transform their health system by making innovation its driving force.¹¹⁰

A system perspective approach to innovation was devised to enable emerging solutions that could be expanded among healthcare providers. The Master Plan also included an innovation management model in which priority is given to initiatives that create value under experimentation, evaluation, and approval.¹¹⁰

How to transition to high value health systems?

Within the framework provided, countries have flexibility in their strategy to transition towards a high value health system model. Three strategies could be pursued when transitioning to a HVHS: (1) extension – extending scope followed by expansion of scale, (2) expansion – expanding scale followed by extension of scope, and (3) transformation – a hybrid approach that simultaneously combines extension with expansion with the introduction of system level transformations.⁶ (See Atun R. Transition to High Value Health Systems: A Primer. Health Systems Innovation Lab. Harvard University, 2022, Boston, MA, USA)

Extension Strategy: extend scope followed by expansion of scale

The *extension strategy* begins with the introduction of a proof-of-concept demonstration of the high-value health system model (Figure 2, Pathway 1) which could include any one or more of the ten HVHS components. The purpose of the demonstration is to design and implement a minimum viable innovation – a working model of the innovation that can be used to produce desired results – to understand system receptivity to the innovation and to inform the strategic change that needs to occur. The demonstration typically consists of an innovation for an episode of care – for a high-volume, time-limited, relatively low-complexity and easily measurable episode of care, for example, a surgical procedure – and is designed for implementation at the department or institution level. With the demonstration, the minimum viable innovation is extended in scope to include additional components of a high value health system to inform the strategic change process, with the introduction of relevant policies and capabilities for the development of an innovation ecosystem to enable readiness for replication and expansion of the demonstration model to other departments, institutions and eventually to system level. An example of the extension strategy

includes the introduction of a demonstration of a high-value health system approach for the management of diabetes in Saudi Arabia (Appendix A, Panel 2).

Figure 2: Pathways to transition to High Value Health System

Source: Atun R. *Transition to High Value Health Systems: A Primer*. Health Systems Innovation Lab. Harvard University, 2022, Boston, MA, USA

Expansion Strategy: expand scale followed by extension of scope

At the start, the *expansion strategy* also involves the introduction of a proof-of-concept demonstration of the high-value health system model which could include any one or more of the ten HVHS components (Figure 2, Pathway 2). However, the pathway followed is one that emphasises the expansion of scale before the extension of the innovation and, as a result, contrasts from the *expansion strategy*. The innovation is expanded from a unit, department or an institution to multiple institutions, networks or the system level. An example of this is Getting it Right First

Time Initiative in the UK where data collection and benchmarking (HVHS component 5) for a surgical episode was expanded from one department, then expanded to multiple institutions before becoming a nationwide initiative (Appendix A, Panel 3). Several other examples have followed the expansion strategy, including, among others, the management of cataracts in Portugal (Appendix A, Panel 4), and type 1 diabetes (Diabeter model) in the Netherlands and internationally (Appendix A, Panel 5)

Transformation Strategy: simultaneous expansion of scope and scale

The *transformation strategy* is a hybrid strategy that emphasises creating an enabling ecosystem for HVHS, together with the rapid expansion of the high-value health system model through the introduction of multiple innovations at different scales with simultaneous expansion of their scope and scale (Figure 3). As lessons are learned, experience is gained, capabilities are built, and a strategic change management program put in place with enabling policies that foster the addition and fortification of the ten components of a high-value health system. The hybrid approach enables novel high value creating innovations to take root at various levels of scope and scale in the system while simultaneously driving major transformations at the system level, with enabling policies for creating ‘push’ and ‘pull’ for innovation generation, design, adoption and diffusion in an ecosystem that fosters ‘emergent’ and ‘driven’ innovations. Examples of a Transformation Strategy to transition to high value health systems include the Catalan Health System (Appendix A, Panel 6), National Collaboration for Value-based Reimbursement and Monitoring of Healthcare (SVEUS) in Sweden (Appendix A, Panel 7) and the Quality and Outcomes Framework in the UK (Appendix A, Panel 8).

Figure 3: Pathway for Transformation Strategy to transition to High Value Health Systems

Source: Atun R. *Transition to High Value Health Systems: A Primer*. Health Systems Innovation Lab. Harvard University, 2022, Boston, MA, USA

References

- 1 World Health Organization, European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, Papanicolas I, *et al.* Health system performance assessment: a framework for policy analysis. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2022 <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/352686> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 2 Frenk J. The World Health Report 2000: Expanding the horizon of health system performance. *Health Policy and Planning* 2010; **25**: 343–5.
- 3 Atun R. Health systems, systems thinking and innovation. *Health Policy and Planning* 2012; **27**: iv4–8.
- 4 Business Dynamics: Systems Thinking and Modeling for a Complex World with CD-ROM: Sterman, John, Sterman, John D.: 9780072389159: Amazon.com: Books. <https://www.amazon.com/Business-Dynamics-Systems-Thinking-Modeling/dp/007238915X> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 5 Forrester JW. System dynamics, systems thinking, and soft OR. *System Dynamics Review (Wiley)* 1994; **10**: 245–56.
- 6 Atun R, Moore G. Building a High-Value Health System. New York: Oxford University Press, 2021 DOI:10.1093/oso/9780197528549.001.0001.
- 7 Atun R, de Jongh T, Secci F, Ohiri K, Adeyi O. A systematic review of the evidence on integration of targeted health interventions into health systems. *Health Policy and Planning* 2010; **25**: 1–14.
- 8 Atun R, De Jongh T, Secci F, Ohiri K, Adeyi O. Integration of targeted health interventions into health systems: A conceptual framework for analysis. *Health Policy and Planning* 2010; **25**: 104–11.
- 9 World Health Organization Maximizing Positive Synergies Collaborative Group. An assessment of interactions between global health initiatives and country health systems. *The Lancet* 2009; **373**: 2137–69.
- 10 Ho CJ, Khalid H, Skead K, Wong J. The politics of universal health coverage. *The Lancet* 2022; **399**: 2066–74.
- 11 Makoni M. Social unrest disrupts South African health care. *The Lancet* 2021; **398**: 287.
- 12 Whitmee S, Haines A, Beyrer C, *et al.* Safeguarding human health in the Anthropocene epoch: report of The Rockefeller Foundation–Lancet Commission on planetary health. *The Lancet* 2015; **386**: 1973–2028.
- 13 Abubakar I. The future of migration, human populations, and global health in the Anthropocene. *The Lancet* 2020; **396**: 1133–4.

- 14 Vos T, Lim SS, Abbafati C, *et al.* Global burden of 369 diseases and injuries in 204 countries and territories, 1990–2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *The Lancet* 2020; **396**: 1204–22.
- 15 Vollset SE, Goren E, Yuan C-W, *et al.* Fertility, mortality, migration, and population scenarios for 195 countries and territories from 2017 to 2100: a forecasting analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study. *The Lancet* 2020; : S0140673620306772.
- 16 Tessema GA, Kinfu Y, Dachew BA, *et al.* The COVID-19 pandemic and healthcare systems in Africa: a scoping review of preparedness, impact and response. *BMJ Global Health* 2021; **6**: e007179.
- 17 Makoni M. The long shadow of COVID-19 in Africa. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine* 2022; **10**: 1016.
- 18 World Economic Outlook, October 2022: Countering the Cost-of-Living Crisis. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/Issues/2022/10/11/world-economic-outlook-october-2022> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).
- 19 DEMOCRACY REPORT 2022 Autocratization Changing Nature? Varieties of Democracy <https://v-dem.net/publications/democracy-reports/> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).
- 20 Global democracy has a very bad year. *The Economist* <https://www.economist.com/graphic-detail/2021/02/02/global-democracy-has-a-very-bad-year> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).
- 21 Health TLD. Digital technologies: a new determinant of health. *The Lancet Digital Health* 2021; **3**: e684.
- 22 Lancet T. Can digital technologies improve health? *The Lancet* 2021; **398**: 1663.
- 23 Atun R, Aydin S, Chakraborty S, *et al.* Universal health coverage in Turkey: Enhancement of equity. *The Lancet* 2013; **382**: 65–99.
- 24 Jamison DT, Summers LH, Alleyne G, *et al.* Global health 2035: a world converging within a generation. *The Lancet* 2013; **382**: 1898–955.
- 25 Atun R, Silva S, Knaul FM. Innovative financing instruments for global health 2002–15: a systematic analysis. *The Lancet Global Health* 2017; **5**: e720–6.
- 26 World Bank Open Data | Data. <https://data.worldbank.org/> (accessed Feb 21, 2019).
- 27 Current health expenditure (% of GDP) - United States | Data. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SH.XPD.CHEX.GD.ZS?locations=US> (accessed June 6, 2020).
- 28 Molina RL, Pace LE. A Renewed Focus on Maternal Health in the United States. *N Engl J Med* 2017; **377**: 1705–7.

- 29 Maternal Mortality Rates in the United States, 2020. 2022; published online Nov 7. <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/hestat/maternal-mortality/2020/maternal-mortality-rates-2020.htm> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).
- 30 Venkataramani AS, O'Brien R, Tsai AC. Declining Life Expectancy in the United States: The Need for Social Policy as Health Policy. *JAMA* 2021; **325**: 621–2.
- 31 Williams DR. Miles to Go before We Sleep: Racial Inequities in Health. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior* 2012; **53**: 279–95.
- 32 Horton R. Offline: Should doctors strike? *The Lancet* 2022; **400**: 1181.
- 33 Striking doctors in breach of ethics - HPCSA. <https://www.iol.co.za/news/south-africa/striking-doctors-in-breach-of-ethics-hpcsa-447172> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).
- 34 Lancet T. Physician burnout: a global crisis. *The Lancet* 2019; **394**: 93.
- 35 Meara JG, Leather AJM, Hagander L, *et al.* Global Surgery 2030: evidence and solutions for achieving health, welfare, and economic development. *The Lancet* 2015; **386**: 569–624.
- 36 Dieleman JL, Campbell M, Chapin A, *et al.* Future and potential spending on health 2015–40: development assistance for health, and government, prepaid private, and out-of-pocket health spending in 184 countries. *The Lancet* 2017; **389**: 2005–30.
- 37 COVIDSurg Collaborative. Elective surgery cancellations due to the COVID-19 pandemic: global predictive modelling to inform surgical recovery plans: Elective surgery during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. *Br J Surg* 2020; published online June 13. DOI:10.1002/bjs.11746.
- 38 Covid-19 – Global Surgery Research. <https://www.globalsurgeryunit.org/global-surgery-research-main/covid-19-related/> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).
- 39 Weiser TG, Haynes AB, Molina G, *et al.* Estimate of the global volume of surgery in 2012: an assessment supporting improved health outcomes. *The Lancet* 2015; **385**: S11.
- 40 Samson B. The difficult clearance of the elective surgical backlog caused by the cancellation of cases due to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Can J Anaesth* 2021; **68**: 932–3.
- 41 Rheumatology TL. Too long to wait: the impact of COVID-19 on elective surgery. *The Lancet Rheumatology* 2021; **3**: e83.
- 42 Massuda A, Hone T, Leles FAG, de Castro MC, Atun R. The Brazilian health system at crossroads: progress, crisis and resilience. *BMJ Glob Health* 2018; **3**: e000829.
- 43 Boston 677 Huntington Avenue. The State of Cardiovascular Disease in G20+ Countries. Health Systems Innovation Lab. 2022; published online May 11. <https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/health-systems-innovation-lab/2022/05/11/cvd-g20/> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).

- 44 Geldsetzer P, Manne-Goehler J, Marcus M-E, *et al.* The state of hypertension care in 44 low-income and middle-income countries: a cross-sectional study of nationally representative individual-level data from 1·1 million adults. *The Lancet* 2019; **394**: 652–62.
- 45 Holmer H, Lantz A, Kunjumen T, *et al.* Global distribution of surgeons, anaesthesiologists, and obstetricians. *The Lancet Global Health* 2015; **3**: S9–11.
- 46 Boniol M, Kunjumen T, Nair TS, Siyam A, Campbell J, Diallo K. The global health workforce stock and distribution in 2020 and 2030: a threat to equity and ‘universal’ health coverage? *BMJ Global Health* 2022; **7**: e009316.
- 47 Barroy H, Sparkes S, Dale E. Assessing fiscal space for health in low and middle income countries: a review of the evidence. 2016. DOI:(WHO/HIS/HGF/ HFWorkingPaper/16.3; Health Financing Working Paper No.3.
- 48 Dowrick C. Patient-centred care for multimorbidity: an end in itself? *The Lancet* 2018; **392**: 4–5.
- 49 Kirksey M, Sasaki M, Grace D, *et al.* A Novel Network-Based Metric of Surgical Team Consistency Opens Opportunities to Improve Hospital Performance and Care Value. *NEJM Catalyst*; **3**: CAT.22.0244.
- 50 Ahmed F, Ahmed N, Briggs TWR, *et al.* Can reverse innovation catalyse better value health care? *The Lancet Global Health* 2017; **5**: e967–8.
- 51 Williams DR, Lawrence JA, Davis BA. Racism and Health: Evidence and Needed Research. *Annual Review of Public Health* 2019; **40**: 105–25.
- 52 Lavizzo-Mourey RJ, Besser RE, Williams DR. Understanding and Mitigating Health Inequities — Past, Current, and Future Directions. *New England Journal of Medicine* 2021; **384**: 1681–4.
- 53 Himmelstein DU, Woolhandler S, Cooney R, McKee M, Horton R. The Lancet Commission on public policy and health in the Trump era. *The Lancet* 2018; **392**: 993–5.
- 54 Ottersen OP, Dasgupta J, Blouin C, *et al.* The political origins of health inequity: prospects for change. *The Lancet* 2014; **383**: 630–67.
- 55 Bossert T. Analyzing the decentralization of health systems in developing countries: decision space, innovation and performance. *Soc Sci Med* 1998; **47**: 1513–27.
- 56 Yau CWH, Leigh B, Liberati E, Punch D, Dixon-Woods M, Draycott T. Clinical negligence costs: taking action to safeguard NHS sustainability. *BMJ* 2020; **368**: m552.
- 57 Lancet T. Medical errors in the USA: human or systemic? *The Lancet* 2011; **377**: 1289.

- 58 How to tame rising US healthcare costs | McKinsey. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/healthcare-systems-and-services/our-insights/how-to-tame-rising-us-healthcare-costs> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).
- 59 Healthcare costs unsustainable in advanced economies without reform - OECD. <https://www.oecd.org/health/healthcarecostsunustainableinadvancedeconomieswithoutreform.htm> (accessed Dec 4, 2022).
- 60 Diseases TLI. Unmet need for COVID-19 therapies in community settings. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases* 2021; **21**: 1471.
- 61 Kleinman A. Four social theories for global health. *The Lancet* 2010; **375**: 1518–9.
- 62 Porter ME, Teisberg EO. Redefining Health Care: Creating Value-based Competition on Results, 1st edition. Harvard Business Review Press, 2006.
- 63 Kruk ME, Gage AD, Arsenault C, *et al.* The Lancet Global Health Commission High-quality health systems in the Sustainable Development Goals era : time for a revolution. 2018; : 1–57.
- 64 Palazuelos D, Farmer PE, Mukherjee J. Community health and equity of outcomes: the Partners In Health experience. *The Lancet Global Health* 2018; **6**: e491–3.
- 65 Herzlinger RE. Why Innovation in Health Care Is So Hard. *Harvard Business Review* 2006; **84**: 58–66.
- 66 Khan M, Abimbola S, Aloudat T, Capobianco E, Hawkes S, Rahman-Shepherd A. Decolonising global health in 2021: a roadmap to move from rhetoric to reform. *BMJ Global Health* 2021; **6**: e005604.
- 67 Keshavjee MDS, Farmer P. Blind Spot: How Neoliberalism Infiltrated Global Health, First edition. Oakland, California: University of California Press, 2014.
- 68 Sauer CM, Chen L-C, Hyland SL, Girbes A, Elbers P, Celi LA. Leveraging electronic health records for data science: common pitfalls and how to avoid them. *The Lancet Digital Health* 2022; **4**: e893–8.
- 69 Safety I of M (US) C on DS for P, Aspden P, Corrigan JM, Wolcott J, Erickson SM. Health Care Data Standards. National Academies Press (US), 2004 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK216088/> (accessed Dec 3, 2022).
- 70 Welcome to the HL7 FHIR Foundation. <https://fhir.org/> (accessed Dec 3, 2022).
- 71 Support tool to strengthen health information systems: Guidance for health information system assessment and strategy development. Copenhagen: World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe, 2021 file:///Users/chereddy/Downloads/9789289055741-eng.pdf.
- 72 Staff PDMG, May 16, 2016, Comments 176 9:25 p m Share on Facebook Share on TwitterView. New \$1.2b Partners computer system brings prescription for frustration - The

- Boston Globe. BostonGlobe.com.
<https://www.bostonglobe.com/business/2016/05/16/partners-healthcare-new-computer-challenges-some-doctors-nurses/1I4QsWGjCJ97xFmUbcDbaj/story.html> (accessed Dec 3, 2022).
- 73 Gawande A. Why Doctors Hate Their Computers. *The New Yorker* 2018; published online Nov 5. <https://www.newyorker.com/magazine/2018/11/12/why-doctors-hate-their-computers> (accessed Dec 3, 2022).
- 74 Microsoft + Nuance: Better Together. <https://news.microsoft.com/nuance/> (accessed Dec 6, 2022).
- 75 National Electronic Healthcare Operator. Armed | About Us.
<https://corporate.armed.am/en/about-us> (accessed Nov 29, 2022).
- 76 Armenia: ArMed national digital health system (2021).
[https://www.who.int/europe/publications/m/item/armenia-armed-national-digital-health-system-\(2021\)](https://www.who.int/europe/publications/m/item/armenia-armed-national-digital-health-system-(2021)) (accessed Nov 29, 2022).
- 77 Story. e-Estonia. <https://e-estonia.com/story/> (accessed Dec 28, 2022).
- 78 Taal H. Health in the Digital Society: the experience of Estonia. *European Journal of Public Health* 2018; **28**: cky213.014b.
- 79 Digital healthcare. e-Estonia. <https://e-estonia.com/programme/digital-healthcare/> (accessed Dec 28, 2022).
- 80 European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, Fahy N, Williams GA. Use of digital health tools in Europe: before, during and after COVID-19. World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe, 2021 <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/345091> (accessed Dec 28, 2022).
- 81 Thiel R, Lucas Deimel, Daniel Schmidtman, *et al.* #SmartHealthSystems International comparison of digital strategies. 2018 https://www.bertelsmann-stiftung.de/fileadmin/files/Projekte/Der_digitale_Patient/VV_SHS-Studie_EN.pdf.
- 82 OECD. Towards an Integrated Health Information System in Korea. Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2022 https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/social-issues-migration-health/towards-an-integrated-health-information-system-in-korea_c4e6c88d-en (accessed Nov 29, 2022).
- 83 Barber SL, Lorenzoni L, Ong P. Price Setting and Price Regulation in Health Care: Lessons for Advancing Universal Health Coverage. OECD, 2019 DOI:10.1787/ed3c16ff-en.
- 84 Pricing Frameworks | IHACPA. <https://www.ihacpa.gov.au/health-care/pricing/pricing-frameworks> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).

- 85 National Health Funding Body. 2022; published online Nov 22.
<https://www.publichospitalfunding.gov.au/> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 86 Understanding the NEP and NEC Determinations 2022–23. Independent Hospital Pricing Authority, 2022 <https://www.ihacpa.gov.au/sites/default/files/2022-08/Understanding%20the%20NEP%20and%20NEC%20Determinations%202022%E2%80%9323.pdf>.
- 87 Assessing performance using PREMs data | CIHI. <https://www.cihi.ca/en/patient-experience-in-canadian-hospitals-2022/assessing-performance-using-prems-data> (accessed Dec 28, 2022).
- 88 ICHOM: Case Studies. ICHOM. <https://www.ichom.org/case-studies/> (accessed Dec 28, 2022).
- 89 Patient-Reported Indicator Surveys (PaRIS) - OECD. <https://www.oecd.org/health/paris/> (accessed Dec 28, 2022).
- 90 Quality and Outcomes Framework (QOF). NHS Digital. <https://digital.nhs.uk/data-and-information/data-tools-and-services/data-services/general-practice-data-hub/quality-outcomes-framework-qof> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 91 Update on Quality Outcomes Framework changes for 2021/22. National Health Service England and National Health Service Improvement, 2021 <https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/B0433-letter-update-on-quality-outcomes-framework-changes-for-21-22.pdf>.
- 92 OECD, World Health Organization. Improving Healthcare Quality in Europe: Characteristics, Effectiveness and Implementation of Different Strategies. OECD, 2019
DOI:10.1787/b11a6e8f-en.
- 93 What we do – Getting It Right First Time – GIRFT. <https://gettingitrightfirsttime.co.uk/what-we-do/> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 94 Reports – Getting It Right First Time – GIRFT. <https://gettingitrightfirsttime.co.uk/girft-reports/> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 95 The Problem of Fragmentation and the Need for Integrative Solutions - PMC.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2653966/> (accessed Nov 29, 2022).
- 96 Integrated delivery systems: the cure for fragmentation - PubMed.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20088632/> (accessed Nov 29, 2022).
- 97 Medicine I of M (US) R on E-B, Yong PL, Saunders RS, Olsen L. Delivery System Integration. National Academies Press (US), 2010
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK53926/> (accessed Nov 29, 2022).

- 98 The ‘3 Beyonds’: Singapore’s strategy to sustain quality healthcare as demand rises | The Straits Times. <https://www.straitstimes.com/singapore/health/the-3-beyonds-singapores-strategy-to-sustain-quality-healthcare-as-demand-rises> (accessed Nov 29, 2022).
- 99 Pereira MJ, Antonio D Molina J, Yijia BT, Gui Jie MY, Ramason R, Tjun Huat IC. Bundled payments for hip fracture surgery are associated with improved access, quality, and healthcare utilization, but higher costs for complex cases: An interrupted time series analysis. *J Orthop Trauma* 2022; published online July 15. DOI:10.1097/BOT.0000000000002459.
- 100 MPs unanimously endorse White Paper on Singapore’s healthcare reform plan - CNA. <https://www.channelnewsasia.com/singapore/mps-unanimously-endorse-healthier-sg-white-paper-singapore-healthcare-reform-plan-2989111> (accessed Nov 29, 2022).
- 101 Michael M. Value-based providers’ payment models: understanding where and under which conditions they work. 2022; : 44.
- 102 2022 MACRA Quality Payment Program. ACS. <https://www.facs.org/advocacy/quality-payment-program-resource-center/2022-macra-quality-payment-program/> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 103 2022 Alternative Payment Models. ACS. <https://www.facs.org/advocacy/quality-payment-program-resource-center/2022-macra-quality-payment-program/apm/> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 104 2022 Merit-based Incentive Payment System. ACS. <https://www.facs.org/advocacy/quality-payment-program-resource-center/2022-macra-quality-payment-program/mips/> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 105 Value-based Procurement - MedTech Europe, from diagnosis to cure. MedTech Europe. <https://www.medtecheurope.org/access-to-medical-technology/value-based-procurement/> (accessed Dec 6, 2022).
- 106 Medtronic. Advantages of Value-Based Procurement. <https://www.medtronic.com/za-en/transforming-healthcare/perspectives-insights-series/neil-fraser-value-based-procurement-advantages.html> (accessed Dec 6, 2022).
- 107 Innovative Procurement Southlake Health Centre | Medtronic. <https://www.medtronic.com/za-en/transforming-healthcare/aligning-value/collaboration-in-healthcare/innovative-procurement-southlake.html> (accessed Dec 5, 2022).
- 108 Struckmann V, Boerma W, van Ginneken E. The Gesundes Kinzigtal programme, Germany. ; : 18.
- 109 Ramos P, Savage C, Thor J, *et al.* It takes two to dance the VBHC tango: A multiple case study of the adoption of value-based strategies in Sweden and Brazil. *Social Science & Medicine* 2021; **282**: 114145.

110 The Catalan Information Systems Master Plan: Building a digital health strategy for Catalonia together. Barcelona: Ministry of Health of the Government of Catalonia, 2017.